

PHARMAAYURVED ONLINE RESEARCH JOURNAL FOR PHARMACY, AYURVED AND ALLIED SCIENCES

<http://www.pharmaayurved.in/>

THE HRIDAYA MARMA–PRANAVAHA SROTAS COMPLEX: AN AYURVEDIC INTERPRETATION AND ITS CORRELATION WITH THE MODERN CARDIORESPIRATORY SYSTEM

Authors:

1. Archana A. Patel, Associate Professor, Department of Rachana Sharir, S.S Agrawal Institute of Ayurveda, Navsari, Gujarat-396445
2. Dhara V. Patel, Assistant Professor, Department Of Rachana Sharira, S.S. Agrawal institute of Ayurveda, Navsari, Gujarat-396445

Citation: Archana A. Patel, Dhara V. Patel, (2026).

***THE HRIDAYA MARMA–PRANAVAHA SROTAS COMPLEX: AN
AYURVEDIC INTERPRETATION AND ITS CORRELATION WITH THE
MODERN CARDIORESPIRATORY SYSTEM.*** In Pharmaayurved

Online Research Journal (Vol.10, Issue 1, pp. 500–505). Pharmaayurved Online
Research Journal. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18730093>

Corresponding author: Dr. Archana A. Patel

Email: archanapatel91@gmail.com

- **Article Received on: 17-02-26**
- **Accepted on: 20-02-26**
- **Published on: 22-02-26**

Abstract

Introduction: In *Ayurveda*, *Hridaya Marma* is regarded as a vital anatomical and functional centre and is classified by the *Acharya Sushruta* as a *Sadhyapranahara Marma*, where injury results in immediate or early death. *Hridaya* is intimately connected with the *Pranavaha Srotas*, serving as one of its *mula* along with the *Maha Srotas*. It is described as the seat of *Praṇa*, *Chetana*, *Manas*, and *Ojas*, thereby playing a central role in the maintenance of life. Modern medical science likewise acknowledges the heart–lung unit as indispensable for circulation, respiration, and systemic homeostasis. The present study seeks to examine the correlation between *Hridaya Marma–Pranavaha Srotas* and the contemporary cardio-respiratory system.

Methods: A conceptual and literary review was undertaken using classical *Ayurvedic* treatises such as the *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita* and *Aṣṭang Hridaya* to analyse the descriptions of *Hridaya Marma* and *Pranavaha Srotas*. These classical view points were systematically compared with modern anatomical and physiological literature pertaining to the heart, lungs, and their associated regulatory structures.

Aim: To correlate the *Ayurvedic* concept of *Hridaya Marma–Pranavaha Srotas* with the contemporary cardio-respiratory system.

Objectives:

- To review classical *Ayurvedic* descriptions of *Hridaya Marma* and *Pranavaha Srotas*.
- To analyse their structural and functional interrelationship.
- To compare the effects of *Hridaya Marma* injury or dysfunction with modern cardio-respiratory disorders.

Results: Classical *Ayurvedic* descriptions of *Hridaya* as the seat of *Praṇa*, *Ojas*, and *Rasa–Rakta Samvahana* parallel modern cardiac functions such as circulation, autonomic regulation, and oxygen transport. *Hridaya* is both a *Marma*, indicating structural vulnerability, and a *Srotomula*, denoting essential physiological function. *Pranavaha Srotas* corresponds to the respiratory passages and pulmonary circulation. Injury to *Hridaya Marma* correlates with acute cardio-respiratory failure, hypoxia, arrhythmias, and sudden death.

Discussion: The combined concept of *Hridaya Marma* and *Pranavaha Srotas* represents an integrated cardio-respiratory unit. *Ayurvedic* explanations emphasize vitality, consciousness, and systemic coordination, complementing modern interpretations. This correlation offers an integrative approach to understanding critical cardio-respiratory conditions and underscores the clinical relevance of *Marma* science in preventive and rehabilitative healthcare.

Key Words:

Pranavaha Srotas, Hridaya, Hridaya Marma, Dosha, Dhatu

INTRODUCTION:

Ayurveda outlines a range of holistic practices aimed at promoting the wellbeing of the mind, body, and spirit. It gives prime importance to *Marma Sharir*, describing *Marma* as vital anatomical sites where *Praṇa* is predominantly situated. Among the 107 *Marmas* described by *Acharya Sushruta*, *Hṛidaya Marma* occupies a central position due to its classification as a *Sadhyapraṇahara Marma* and vital point in *Ayurveda* that has been studied for centuries because of its unique location and importance in maintaining overall health and well-being, where trauma leads to immediate or early death.

Hṛidaya is not only a structural organ but also a vital functional entity described as the seat of *Praṇa*, *Chetana*, *Manas*, and *Ojas*. *Pranavaha Srotas* is the channel responsible for the movement of *Prana* (vital life energy) and is closely associated with respiration and oxygen delivery. *Ayurvedic Samhitas* describe its origin, functions, causes of dysfunction, and related disorders in various contexts. According to *Charaka* in *Vimana Sthana*, *Srotas* are channels that enable the circulation of vital elements, and the *Mula Sthana* of *Pranavaha Srotas* is identified as the *Hridaya* (heart) and *Mahasrotas*¹ emphasizing its role in respiration and maintenance of life.

Modern medical science recognizes the heart and lungs as an integrated cardio-respiratory system, responsible for circulation, gas exchange, and homeostasis. Dysfunction of this system leads to rapid physiological deterioration and death. The conceptual similarity between these descriptions forms the basis for the present correlation study.

Aim

To correlate the *Ayurvedic* concept of *Hṛidaya Marma–Pranavaha Srotas* with the contemporary cardio-respiratory system.

Objectives

- To review classical *Ayurvedic* descriptions of *Hṛidaya Marma* and *Pranavaha Srotas*.
- To analyse their structural and functional interrelationship.
- To compare the effects of *Hṛidaya Marma* injury or dysfunction with modern cardio-respiratory disorders.

Materials & Methods

- The present study is a conceptual and literary review.
- Primary references were collected from classical *Ayurvedic* texts including *Charaka Samhita*, *Susruta Samhita*. Relevant verses related to *Hṛidaya Marma* and *Praṇavaha Srotas* were analyzed.

These concepts were compared with modern anatomical and physiological descriptions of the heart, lungs, pulmonary circulation, and autonomic nervous system as described in standard modern medical textbooks. Correlation was established based on structural, functional, and pathological similarities.

Review literature

Etymology:

According to *Brihat Aranyak*, the word — *Hridaya* is made up of three *Dhatu* (verbs) — *Hru* stands for *Harati* (to receive), *Da* for *Dadati* (to give or contribute) & *Ya* stands for *Yagati*, which means to control or to move which refers to the rhythmic movement for collecting and diffusing of *Prana*.

Swaroop:

- The shape of heart is compared with an inverted (downward facing) lotus bud.²

- *Marma* is defined as an anatomical site where five structures—*Mamsa* (muscles), *Sira* (vessels/conducting system), *Snayu* (ligaments and supporting structures), *Asthi* (bones), and *Sandhi* (joints)—converge and where *Prana* (life force) naturally resides.

Location:

Heart is situated in the thoracic cavity, positioned between the two *Stanas* (breasts). It is located above the *Amashaya dwara*. It is a site of qualities of mind i.e *Sattva*, *Raja* and *Tamagnas*.³

Pramana:

In humans, the heart is roughly comparable in sized to a

clenched fist. *Hridaya* extends into the area of *Chaturangula* (four finger).⁴

Hridaya as *marma* Classification:

- Dimention- 4 *Angul*
- Effect- *Sadhya Pranahara Marma*
- *Shadanganusar- Urogata Marma*
- Structural basis- *Sira Marma*
- Number- 1

Marma abhighat lakshana:

Injury can cause immediate or severe threat to life. Trauma or disease affecting *Hridaya* disrupts *Prana*, *Ojas*, and *Sadhaka Pitta*, leading to serious systemic consequences.

Regional anatomy of Hridaya Marma:⁵

Mamsa- Cardiac muscles.

Sira- Coronary vessels, Arch of aorta & its branches.

Snayu- S.A. node, A.V. node, Purkinjii fibres, bundles of His, Vagus nerve, Cardiac plexus.

Asthi- Tendinous Fibrous skeleton, Sternum, 2nd, 3rd, 4th ribs.

Sandhi- Posterior aspect of Sterno-costal joint.

Hridaya as mula sthana of Pranavaha srotas:

The *mula sthana* of *Pranavaha srotas* are *Hridaya*^{6,7} is explained by *Acharya charak* and *Sushruta*. The word *Hridaya* clearly related to heart, and we all know the heart is the only organ by which the oxygen is able to supply to each and every tissue by its pumping mechanism, so only heart can accomplish this function independently with out much dependent on other organ. *Pranavaha Srotas* is responsible for the circulation of *Prana* and is essential for respiration and vitality. If we look at the *dushti lakshana* of *Pranavaha srotas* of *Charaka* and *Sushruta* most of them are seen as disturbance in the process of respiration. Injury or vitiation leads to symptoms like *Shwasa*

(dyspnea), *Kasa* (cough), chest pain, palpitations, and loss of consciousness. Severe damage may result in rapid deterioration and death due to disturbance of *Prana*.

Structural or functional heart damage in modern medicine corresponds to injury of *Hridaya Marma* in *Ayurveda*.

Cardiopulmonary failure parallels dysfunction of *Pranavaha Srotas*, affecting oxygenation and life force circulation.

Heart Anatomy and Physiology:⁸

According to modern, the heart is a hollow, muscular organ situated in the mediastinum between the lungs. It is composed of four chambers—two atria and two ventricles—separated by septa and regulated by atrioventricular and semilunar valves that ensure unidirectional blood flow. The heart wall consists of three layers: epicardium, myocardium, and endocardium, with the myocardium responsible for contractile function. The coronary circulation supplies oxygen and nutrients to the cardiac tissue.

Physiologically, the heart functions as a rhythmic pump that maintains continuous blood circulation through the cardiac cycle. Its electrical activity originates in the sinoatrial (SA) node and is conducted through the atrioventricular (AV) node, bundle of His, bundle branches, and Purkinje fibres, enabling coordinated atrial and ventricular contractions.

Integration with the Cardiorespiratory and Autonomic Nervous Systems:

The heart works in synchrony with the respiratory system to facilitate oxygenation of blood and removal of carbon dioxide. Deoxygenated blood is sent to the lungs for gas exchange, while oxygenated blood is returned to the left heart for systemic distribution, thereby supporting tissue oxygenation and metabolic balance.

Cardiac function is controlled by the autonomic nervous system. Sympathetic stimulation increases heart rate and contractility during stress or activity, whereas parasympathetic input via the vagus nerve decreases heart rate at rest, enabling adaptive cardiovascular regulation.

Discussion

Hridaya, described in *Ayurveda* as the seat of *Prana*, *Ojas*, and *Rasa-Rakta Samvahana*, closely corresponds to modern cardiac functions such as blood circulation, oxygen transport, and metabolic support. *Pranavaha Srotas*, with *Hridaya* and *Mahasrotas* as its roots, can be correlated with the respiratory passages, lungs, and pulmonary circulation.

Injury to *Hridaya Marma* results in symptoms such as dyspnea, severe pain, loss of consciousness, and death, which parallel modern clinical conditions including acute cardiorespiratory failure, hypoxia, arrhythmias, and shock. The dual description of *Hridaya* as both a *Marma* (vital point) and *Srotomula* (functional origin) underscores its essential life-sustaining role.

Ayurvedic texts portray *Hridaya* as a multidimensional entity integrating structural, physiological, and psychological functions. Its association with *Pranavaha Srotas* reflects a holistic view of respiration and circulation as inseparable life processes. Modern physiology supports this perspective by emphasizing the functional interdependence of the heart and lungs. Concepts such as *Chetana* and *Manas* residing in *Hridaya* may be correlated with autonomic and neuro-cardiac regulation, while *Ojas* can be conceptually linked to immunity and vitality, both of which are compromised in chronic cardiorespiratory disorders.

In modern medical science, major risk factors for heart disease include age, hypertension, diabetes, obesity, smoking, sedentary lifestyle, and psychological stress. Cardiac injury may occur due to ischemia, myocardial infarction, inflammation, trauma, or electrical disturbances, leading to reduced cardiac output and impaired tissue oxygenation.

In *Ayurveda*, *Hridaya* is classified as a *Sadhya Pranahara Marma*, where injury is potentially fatal. *Charaka* who has given separate space for *Hridaya* in *Trimarma Adhyay*. It is also recognized as the *Moola Sthana* of *Praṇavaha Srotas*, along with the *Mahasrotas*. Etiological factors such as improper diet, excessive exertion, suppression of natural urges, trauma, and mental stress vitiate *Praṇavaha Srotas*, manifesting as dyspnoea, chest discomfort, palpitations, and loss of consciousness.

Thus, structural and functional cardiac pathology described in modern medicine can be correlated with injury to *Hridaya Marma* and dysfunction of *Praṇavaha Srotas* in *Ayurveda*, highlighting a shared recognition of the heart's central role in sustaining life.

Conclusion

Ayurvedic concepts of *Hridaya Marma*, and *Praṇavaha Srotas* demonstrate a comprehensive understanding of the heart as a vital centre integrating circulation, respiration, and life force. The correlation of *Hridaya* with modern cardiac anatomy and physiology, and *Praṇavaha Srotas* with the cardiorespiratory system, highlights strong conceptual parallels between *Ayurvedic* and contemporary medical perspectives. Injury or dysfunction of *Hridaya Marma* leading to fatal outcomes aligns with modern descriptions of acute cardiac and respiratory failure. The convergence of *Ayurvedic* and modern views underscores the enduring relevance of *Hridaya* in maintaining life, vitality, and systemic balance.

REFERENCES:

1. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, *Charaka Samhita of Charak & Dradhhabala, Charaka Chandrika Hindi commentary, Vimana sthana, chapter 5, verse no 3,8, Varanasi, Chaukhambha Surbharti Prakashan, edition 2023.*
2. Dr. Bhaskar Govind Ghanekar, *Sushruta Samhita of Sushruta, Shareer sthana, chapter 4, verse no.32, 1st Edition, New Delhi; Meharchand, Lachhmandas Publication, Reprint Jan 2018.*
3. Dr. Bhaskar Govind Ghanekar, *Sushruta Samhita of Sushruta, Shareer sthana, chapter 6, verse no.34, 1st Edition, New Delhi; Meharchand, Lachhmandas Publication, Reprint Jan 2018.*
4. Dr. Bhaskar Govind Ghanekar, *Sushruta Samhita of Sushruta, shareer sthana, chapter 6, verse no.30, 1st Edition, New Delhi; Meharchand, Lachhmandas Publication, Reprint Jan 2018.*
5. Pragati R Bachikwar, Aparna Wanare, Yajurved N Selokar, and Gopal Sharma. Study of Hriday Marma with special reference to modern anatomy. Department of Rachana Sharir, Government Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Nagpur, Maharashtra.
6. Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, *Charaka Samhita of Charak & Dradhhabala, Charaka Chandrika Hindi commentary, Vimana sthana, chapter 5, verse no.8, Varanasi, Chaukhambha Surbharti Prakashan, edition 2023*
7. Dr. Bhaskar Govind Ghanekar, *Sushruta Samhita of Sushruta, shareer sthana, chapter 9, verse no.12, 1st Edition, New Delhi; Meharchand, Lachhmandas Publication, Reprint Jan 2018.*
8. Tortora GJ, Derrickson BH. *Principles of Anatomy and Physiology, 15th edition, Hoboken (NJ): John Wiley & Sons; 2017, chapter 20, page no. 757.*